

EVALUATION OF PHYSICAL FITNESS OF THE RESIDENTS IN THE RESIDENTIAL AND NURSING HOME WITH „THE TIMED UP AND GO” TEST

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Summary

Introduction: More and more patients benefit from rehabilitation in advanced age, which is caused by aging of the society. In this group of patients, various injuries and diseases cause a significant reduction in physical fitness. Physical activity is one of the essential parts of a healthy lifestyle and is a basic determiner of physical fitness. Lack of this activity is a major cause of health loss.

Objective: To present and evaluate the physical fitness of people over 60 residing in the Residential and Nursing Home using "The Timed Up and Go" test.

Material and Methods: The research included thirty residents of the Dr Leon Szuman Residential and Nursing Home in Torun. The research included people who were able to get up from a chair and walk 6 meters without the assistance of others. The research included eighteen women and twelve men aged over 60 years. The research was about to complete a questionnaire by a researched person and perform "The Timed Up and Go" test. During the test, the time was measured.

Results: The average duration of the test completion of reaserached people was 12.25 seconds. Physically active people have received better average time than physically inactive ones. Increased physical activity affected the reduction of test time. Men participating in the research received better average test time than women. The difference came to over a second.

Conclusions: Physical activity in advanced age is a very important factor in prolonging life and keeping people's health as good as possible.

Introduction

According to Alex Comfort, "aging is characterized by inability to maintain homeostasis under conditions of physiological stress and this weakness is connected with decreasing vitality and increasing one's sensitivity." [1]

There are high requirements imposed on the health service thanks to a growing average of the lifespan. Even in the interwar years, the lifespan did not cross 50, nowadays people live past the age of 70. Significant increase in people in advanced age has a vital influence on social, economic and health policies in countries around the world. [2, 3]

More and more patients benefit from rehabilitation in advanced age, which is caused by aging of the society. A very important factor in treating these people is an appropriate rehabilitation which helps restore or maintain the ability to live independently. [4]

Trying to anticipate the further existence of the elderly in the society, the possibility of practical application of different tests to assess physical fitness should be considered. Applying these tests and subsequent changes in treatment are necessary to improve the quality of care, to set new directions of rehabilitation and to possibly affect the cost of treatment. [2]

Physical activity is one of the essential parts of a healthy lifestyle and is a basic determiner of physical fitness. Lack of this activity is a major cause of health loss. It can lead to diseases such as heart attack or stroke, coronary heart disease, diabetes or hypertension. Physical activity decreases with age. Older people exercise less and less regularly than younger people. However, it is the physical activity in advanced age which delays involuntional processes, contributes to the well-being, as well as reduces the risk of civilization diseases and improves the quality of life. [5, 6, 7]

According to Przewęda, physical fitness is an integrated set of three individual factors: - the efficiency of physical fitness and the level of motor skills, - motor skills, - motivation and subjective involvement in the activities. [8]

Jan Szopa characterizes by the concept of physical fitness as follows: "physical fitness is the integrity of human capacity and skills to enable effective performance of all motor tasks." [9]

According to Chromiński, fitness depends on one's genetic characteristics, such as motor abilities, somatic constitution, the efficiency of the senses, temperament and the right proportions of

the body. This is a set of an endogenous factors. The second set of factors – exogenous factors - refers to the external environment and lifestyle. Many a time we meet up with the concept of general and special physical fitness. General physical fitness is a certain level of development, forming of motor skills or motor structures considered as a complex. Special physical fitness is the advancement of forming fitness and technical skills in specific disciplines or sports competitions. According to the above author, mobility is the ability to move one's motor system through mastering basic motor habits. The increase in mobility depends on acquired skills and personal experience. Physical fitness can be defined as a current ability to perform any motor functions and to develop motor skills, such as strength, speed, agility and other motor abilities. Physical fitness and mobility form motoricity and reflect the results of ontogenetic development. In the topic of the physical development, the issues of motor development become of particular significance, since this development reflects many our manners, skills and abilities. [10]

Trzeźniowski defines physical fitness as willingness of the human body to take up and solve difficult motor tasks in different situations in life, which require strength, speed, flexibility, agility and stamina, as well as some acquired and shaped motor skills and motor habits based on relevant movement skills and health condition. [11]

Physical exercise is a repetitive physical activity, which aims to maintain or increase physical fitness. [12]

In the course of life, there are a lot of changes in the human body, the older a man becomes, the more catabolic reactions predominate over anabolic ones, causing many different changes in the human body.

Disturbances in the mechanisms of neural and hormonal regulation make it difficult to maintain homeostasis in the elderly. Activity of the senses declines with the course of age. Difficulty in walking increases. Posture stability deteriorates. The response time extends. Connective tissue becomes stiffer. Thermoregulation deteriorates. The articular symptoms are enhanced. The basic metabolism reduces. Lungs biological capacity decreases and the volume of dead space increases. The activity of enzymes of aerobic and anaerobic processes is reduced. The height of the body reduces. Mineral content in bones becomes lower. Exercise capacity after reaching the maximum reduces by approximately 1% per year. The maximum frequency of heart rate reduces. The stroke volume of the heart and maximal oxygen uptake reduces. There are shortness of breath during exercise. The ability to perform longer physical exercises reduces. Blood pressure during maximal effort is higher.

Achieving a functioning takes more time. Muscle strength decreases due to the reduces muscle mass. Mobility decreases due to lower stability and muscle strength. The maximum muscle strength decreases after the age of 40 by about 1% per year. [13]

Despite these significant changes in the body, physical training of older people can improve the strength of skeletal muscles, aerobic capacity, and thus allows to maintain a healthy body until death. In the elderly, endurance training and strength training can be as effective as in younger people. Pains in the lumbar spine may be counterbalanced by an appropriate strength training. Please note that the risk associated with the performing the exercises is significantly lower than the expected benefits. [13]

The UN General Assembly in 1973 adopted a resolution concerning the people in the geriatric age. UN in recent research argues that population aging is a permanent, common and irreversible process, and that the average lifespan on Earth increases. Currently, the average lifespan on Earth is about 66 years. Every tenth person in the world is over 60 years old, however, in 2050 every fifth person will be of this age. The number of centenarians (aged 100 and older) will increase 14-fold from approximately 265,000 in 2005 to 3.7 million in 2050. There is a very large geographical diversity, only one in twenty people in Africa is over 60, in Europe, every fifth person. The pace of aging is higher in developing societies than in developed societies. [14, 15]

In Poland, people aged over 65 are the fastest growing group of people. According to the UN, the so called 'threshold of demographic advanced age' is 7%. Poland has already exceeded it in

1966. 40 years later, this threshold was already over 13%. In 2008, the average life expectancy for men in Poland was 71 years old and for women 79.8 years. Number of people in Poland amounts to over 38 million, there are more than 5 million people over the age of 65, which is 13.5% of the Polish population. The median age for Poles is 37.5 and is growing every year. According to the forecast, the Polish population is to be reduced to about 36 million until 2035. At the same time, people over 65 are going to become approximately 23% of the population. [14, 15, 16, 17, 18]

Fig. 1 A forecast of the Polish population over 65 years old [17]

Fig. 2 A forecast of the Polish population over 65 - men [17]

Fig. 3 A forecast of the Polish population over 65 - women [17]

According to the research conducted in 2004 by the Central Statistical Office, over 97% of

people aged over 60 perform activities which do not require physical effort (eg reading, watching television), over 63% perform activities which require slightly intensive effort (eg walking, cycling), approximately 20% perform recreational sport or work in the garden, less than 0.5% perform professional sports. [19]

Fig. 4 A way of spending leisure time by people over 60 years old [19]

In Poland in 2004, among people aged 60 and over, there were 46% of disabled people, 11% of pronounced legally as disabled, 13% of only biologically disabled people (perceived efficiency reduction), 21% of both legally and biologically disabled. In 1996, among the disabled Poles, 26% of people were pronounced disabled only legally, 15% were pronounced disabled biologically and almost 59% both legally and biologically. [19, 20, 25,26]

Fig. 5 Disability among people over 60 years old in Poland [19]

According to the Research of Central Statistical Office in 2004, only 7.5% of people over 60

were economically active. [19]

Fig. 6 Activity of people over age 60 in Poland [19]

People after 60 years old evaluated their health condition as follows: very good about 1.5%, good about 15%, neither good nor bad over 46%, bad over 28%, very bad over 7.5%. [19]

Fig. 7 Assessment of the health condition of people aged over 60 in Poland [19]

Gait disorders are a major cause of loss of physical fitness in elder patients and lead to the impaired quality of life, they increase the possibility of falling. According to Tinetti research, 30% of people who have crossed 65 years old fall down each year, and a quarter of these patients suffer serious injury because of the fall. [21] The cause of gait disorders often consists of many factors. Gait disorders can be caused by sensory disturbances, myelopathy, strokes, Parkinson's disease, cerebellar diseases, and many other reasons, including psychogenic or toxic reasons. [22, 23, 24]

The speed of gait in young people is 1,3-1,6 m / s and is reducing every year by about 0,1-0,7%. Lower walking speed is mainly caused by shortening a step, which is 60 cm and is reducing by approximately 4% between twenty and sixty years old. In the elderly who are less skilled the step can reduce to 20 cm. [24]

To assess the gait, different tests are used. One of the frequently used is "The Timed Up and Go" test.

Aim of the research

1. To present and evaluate the physical fitness of people over 60 residing in the Residential and Nursing Home using "The Timed Up and Go" test.
2. To assess the risk of falls among nursing home residents and present the differences of acquired test time between physically active people and people who do not perform any sports.
3. To present the recommendations of exercises which increase the abilities of motion in elder people.

Materials and methods

The research involved thirty residents of the Dr Leon Szuman Residential and Nursing Home in Torun. The research included people who were able to get up from a chair and walk 6 meters without the assistance of others. The research excluded people moving in a wheelchair and those with neurological diseases. The research included eighteen women and twelve men aged over 60 years with whom the logical-verbal contact was possible. The average age was 76.27 years (standard deviation $\sigma=9.31$), for men 75.42 ($\sigma=9.22$), for women 76.83 ($\sigma=9.59$).

The research was about to complete only once a questionnaire by a researched person. The questionnaire included the questions concerning:

Time of stay in the RNH:

Physical activity: MINIMUM SMALL MEDIUM LARGE INTENSIVE

Sport (swimming, jogging / brisk walking / Nordic walking, aerobics, dance):

... ..

Pain hindering movement: YES NO

Mobility:

-Alone

-With a stick

-In a wheelchair

-With a walker

Self-independence in daily activities:

-Washing/ morning washing routine

-Dressing

-Eating

-Bathing

The occurrence of falls: YES NO

Fear of falling: YES NO

Characteristics of falls:

-Number of falls in the last year:

-Consequences in the form of severe trauma (fracture, immobilization)

-A place where there was a fall (outside the home, at home: the kitchen, the bathroom)

-Circumstances of the fall (standing up, sitting, walking, bending)

-Type of shoes worn at the time of a fall (bare feet, slippers, shoes with low / high heels)

Symptoms prior to the fall:

-Dizziness

-Palpitations

-Chest pain

-Shortness of breath

-Weakness

-Dizziness before my eyes

-Loss of consciousness

The research also included completing once "The Timed Up and Go" test. During the test, the time was measured. Time measurements were made using an electronic stopwatch with an accuracy of 0.1 seconds. "The Timed Up and Go" test was designed to assess physical fitness, ability to maneuver rapidly and maintain dynamic balance. [4, 18, 24, 29, 30, 31]

According to Podsiadlo, people who can perform the test in less than 20 seconds can stand up alone from the toilet, a chair, can maintain static and dynamic balance, and have a walking pace (more than 0.5 meter per second), which is sufficient to cross the street. [7]

Non-disabled people do the test in less than 10 seconds. People impaired need a minimum of 20 seconds to complete the test. Time over 14 seconds may indicate an increased risk of falls. [18]

Table I Most common diseases in the group of subjects-comparison by gender

	Circulatory system diseases	Motor system illnesses	Both circulatory system and motor system diseases
Number of men	7	3	2
Number of women	11	7	0

Fig. 8 Shows the time of stay of residents in a nursing home. The largest number of residents (14 people) stay in the center for less than 5 years, one person stays in the center for over 20 years.

Fig. 8. Time of stay of residents in nursing home

Table 2 shows the subjective evaluation of physical activity of people tested. The largest number of people described themselves as a person of average physical activity (13 people). Nobody has said that their physical activity is intense.

Table II Subjective assessment of physical activity of nursing home residents

Subjective assessment of physical activity	minimum	small	medium	high	intensive
Number of people	3	11	13	3	0

Fig. 9. Shows the sports activities of the respondents. Most people from the thirty-person group have ensured that they perform physical exercise (22 people).

Fig. 9. Playing sport in the research group.

In the thirty-person group analyzed, during the interview eleven people reported the occurrence of pain that made it difficult to move. The other nineteen people did not report the occurrence of such pain.

Table III The occurrence of pain hindering the movement in the research group

Total number of people reporting the pain hindering movement	11
Number of women reporting the pain hindering movement	7
Number of men reporting the pain hindering movement	4
Total number of people not reporting the pain hindering movement	19
Number of women not reporting the pain hindering movement	11
Number of men not reporting the pain hindering movement	8

Among all those surveyed, twenty-one people moved by themselves, other people used a walking stick, crutches or moved using the walker.

Table IV Characteristics of movement of people in the research group.

The way of movement	Independently	Stick/crutches	Walker
Total number of people	21	7	2
Number of women	12	4	2
Number of men	9	3	0

Results.

The average time of „The Timed Up and Go” test among the 30 people researched in the Nursing Home was 12,25 seconds ($\sigma=4,83$). Times obtained by men and women are presented separately in table V.

Table V Average test time according to gender (in seconds).

	Total	Men	Women
Average test time	12,25 ± 4,83	11,47 ± 4,81	12,76 ± 4,91

In Table VI there are average results of the test according the age and gender. The best results were achieved by men aged 60-69 years (8.17 seconds). The worst times were achieved by women aged 70-79 years (15.75 seconds).

Table VI Average test time in seconds according to age and gender.

	Total	Men	Women
60-69	9,95 ± 3,27	8,17 ± 2,35	11,02 ± 3,49
70-79	14,75 ± 7,79	13,54 ± 6,32	15,75 ± 5,82
80-89	11,59 ± 2,11	11,93 ± 3,61	11,42 ± 1,36
90-99	10,65 ± 1,34	9,7	11,6

According to one's own subjective assessment of physical activity, people were divided into four groups. The group with minimum physical activity achieved the worst times (average 18.67 seconds), a group with high physical activity achieved the best average test time (8.9 seconds).

Table VII Average test time in seconds according to gender and physical activity

	Total	Men	Women
Minimum	18,67 ± 10,49	12,9 ± 4,53	30,2
Small	13,14 ± 4,38	14,35 ± 6,98	12,23 ± 2,39
Medium	10,9 ± 2,23	9,78 ± 0,77	11,6 ± 2,59
High	8,9 ± 3,04	5,6	10,55 ± 1,49

According to research by Podsiadlo, time below 20 seconds is obtained by people who are able to independently stand up from a chair and maintain dynamic balance. People impaired need more than 20 seconds. Fit people do this test in less than 10 seconds and the time over 14 seconds increases the risk of falls. [7, 18]

Table VIII Number of people in different time intervals

Time	Less than 10 sec.	10-14 sec.	14-20 sec.	More than 20 sec.
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Number of people	10	15	3	2
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The research included nine people who normally use the orthopedic equipment to move independently. The division was made into people who move without any help and people who need orthopedic equipment to move, including crutches, canes, walkers. Table IX shows the average time of residents divided into the patients using, or not, orthopedic equipment. Those who did not need help achieved generally better test time, with the average of more than 3 seconds.

Table IX Average test time in seconds according to the use of orthopedic equipment

	Total	Men	Women
Independently	11,26 ± 3,77	11,66 ± 5,57	10,96 ± 1,77
With the use of orthopedic equipment	14,56 ± 4,06	10,93 ± 1,63	16,37 ± 7,19

The residents determined whether during the performing the physical exercises they felt a pain hindering the movement. Eleven people responded positively. Table X shows the average time obtained by patients who felt pain or pain did not exist. People who did not feel the pain hindering movement achieved average time (11.66 seconds) than people who felt this pain (13.26 seconds).

Table X Average test time in seconds according to feeling the pain

	Total	Men	Women
Occurance of pain	13,26 ± 6,03	10,32 ± 1,8	14,94 ± 7,06
Lack of pain	11,66 ± 4,05	12,05 ± 5,82	11,37 ± 2,37

Each of the respondents mentioned at least one of the following diseases: cardiovascular diseases or diseases of the musculoskeletal system, so that all patients were divided considering these diseases. Patients with disorders of the musculoskeletal system achieved better average test times than patients with cardiovascular diseases. The difference amounted to more than 1.5 second.

Table XI Average test time in secondo according to disease

	Total	Men	Women
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Circulatory system diseases	12,89 ± 5,93	12,36 ± 6,17	13,24 ± 6,06
Motor system illnesses	11,4 ± 2,34	9,97 ± 1,36	12,01 ± 2,48
Both circulatory system and motor system diseases	10,65 ± 3,04	10,65 ± 3,04	X

Patients were divided due to the time of stay in the nursing home. The best average time was gained by patients who stay in the resort between 11-15 years. The worst time was gained by patients who stay less than 5 years. The difference was about 4 seconds.

Table XII Average test time in seconds according to the time of stay in nursing home

	Total	Men	Women
Less than 5 years	13,01 ± 4,33	14,46 ± 6,28	12,66 ± 2,79
6- 10 years	12,86 ± 6,22	9,97 ± 0,36	14,78 ± 7,65
11- 15 years	9,05 ± 2,61	8,5 ± 4,1	9,6 ± 1,56
16- 20 years	11,6		11,6
21-25 years	8,9		8,9

When asked about physical activity, twenty-two declared that they undertake such activity in leisure time. Thus, the division into two groups was made. The group which did not demonstrate a willingness to take up physical activity achieved by nearly 2.5 seconds worse average test time than the group who participated in physical activity.

Table XII Average test time in secondo according to physical activity undertaken

	Total	Men	Women
Physically active	11,6 ± 3,79	12,09 ± 5,47	11,25 ± 2,22
Lack of physical activity	14,04 ± 6,96	9,63 ± 0,9	16,68 ± 7,82

The correlation between physical activity of the surveyed and "The Timed Up and Go" test times was examined. The correlation coefficient was -0.9659. Thus, there is a very strong negative relationship between test times obtained and physical activity. The higher physical activity, the

lower the time of test is.

Table XIII The relationship between the average time test obtained and a physical activity

Physical activity	Minimum	Small	Medium	High
Average test time (sec.)	18,67	13,14	10,9	8,9

Fig 10. The relationship between the average time test obtained and a physical activity

The correlation between the time of stay of the surveyed in the Social Welfare House and the average test time was examined. The correlation coefficient was -0.7484. The relationship between the two measured factors is strong. The longer stay in the resort is, the lower the test time was.

Table XIV The relationship between the average test time and the time of stay in the resort

Time of stay in the resort	Less than 5 years	6-10 years	11-15 years	16-20 years	21-25 years
Average test time (sec.)	13,01	12,86	9,05	11,6	8,9

Fig. 11. The relationship between the average test time and the time of stay in the resort

The correlation between the age of the respondents and the average test time. The correlation coefficient was -0.06443. The results showed no correlation connection.

Table XV The relationship between the average time obtained and the respondents' age

Age	60- 69	70- 79	80- 89	90- 99
Average test time (sec.).	9,95	14,75	11,59	10,65

Discussion

Physical activity is a very important factor in enhancing the quality of life in advanced age. The selection of intensity and type of exercises is very individual. When selecting exercises, one's physical fitness is considered mainly. The exercises for the elderly should be regular and contain an endurance, stretching and power unit. Insufficient physical activity has an influence on mental health causing its reduction. [32, 33]

According to research by Charzewski, people aged 60 rarely do sports. According to him, 20% of people aged over 60 do gymnastics, and 20% of women and 30% of men ride a bike. Most of the people doing regular sports are women. Drygas reports that about 70% of men do not exercise at all. According to research by Drabik, 55% of older people go walking. This coincides with our research, where more than 60% of nursing home residents go walking. [5, 34, 35]

Zak in his research concluded that exercises which last three months improve physical fitness of older people and increase the speed of gait. Similar conclusions were reached by Hu and Woollacott, who have shown in their studies that a 4-week training improves physical fitness of older people. According to other studies by Zak, rehabilitation which lasts three months in about 30% of patients gave better results of "The Timed Up and Go" test. By another research by Zak, a three-month rehabilitation, during which Thera-Band® tapes were used, 62.5% of patients showed improved results of "The Timed Up and Go" test. A similar group of respondents, divided according to the disease, participated in our research. Judge and his colleagues also claimed the improvement in gait during the rehabilitation of elderly patients, which lasted 12 weeks. During the rehabilitation, equivalent exercises and resistance exercises were applied. Fiatarone and colleagues using also

found the improvement in gait in people who were over 90 years, using a comprehensive rehabilitation program. According to the data contained in an article in Clinical Rehabilitation journal, forty-minute exercises performed 2-3 times a week for 3 months significantly increase physical fitness of older people and improve protection from dangerous falls. Scientists from Japan have used "The Timed Up and Go" test during the research. Other researchers, who have used the test mentioned, were the French scientists who examined the risk of falls in people over 60 years old. [30, 31, 36, 37, 38, 39, 40, 41].

Recommendations of exercises for older people

According to World Health Organization, elderly people should select endurance exercises, strength training and stretching during physical activity. Endurance exercises (eg running, cycling) should be performed 2 times a week for about 20 minutes. Pulse should be no higher than 40 - 60% above the resting heart rate. Strengthening exercises should also be carried out 2 times a week for about 20 minutes. Each exercise should be repeated 10 to 15 times. To prevent the contracture of important muscle groups and not to lead to significant loss of physical fitness and self-reliance, stretching exercises should be performed daily for about 5 - 10 minutes. [18, 24, 32, 42]

Exercises for older people should be relatively easy, should give joy and relax. According to various studies, physical activity in older people causes the reduction of mortality because of cardio-respiratory reasons. Exercises may prolong the period of independence for 8 - 14 years. The elderly should apply various types of equivalent exercises which increase a sense of stability and reduce the risk of falling. According to studies by Zak, to learn how to change the position safely and to stand up independently after the fall, the reverse learning of movements is better than the traditional method of learning. [18, 24, 32, 33, 36, 42, 43]

Sample exercises for older people: Starting position (SP) – lie on the back, legs bent, feet based on the ground Movement - shift the ball from hand to hand with a raised, bent leg. SP – lie on the back, legs bent, feet based on the ground, the ball kept with both hands on the stomach. Movement – shift the two upper limbs with the ball in behind one's head - inhale through nose, return of the upper limbs to the stomach - exhale through mouth. SP – lie on the back, legs bent, feet based on the ground, the ball between the knees. Movement - squeeze the ball with the knees, endure – inhale through nose, relax - exhale through mouth. SP - lie ahead, legs straight, hands under chin. Movement – lift left lower limb once and right lower limb once. SP - lie ahead, legs straight, hands under chin. Movement - lift in turns upper and lower limbs - the left upper limb and lower right limb, then right upper limb and left lower limb. SP - lie ahead, legs straight, hands under chin. Movement - blow the ball. SP - lie ahead, legs straight, hands under chin. Movement - hold the ball on the buttocks, tense the buttocks. SP – simple kneeling. Movement - lift the upper limbs with the ball up – inhale, the hips up. Sit on the heels, lower the upper limbs with the ball on the thigh - exhale through the mouth.

Conclusions

1. The average test time of the people researched was 12.25 seconds, people who received such results can maintain static and dynamic balance and do not need help to stand up from a chair or a toilet.
2. Men participating in the research received better average time of "The Timed Up and Go" than women by over a second. This indicates a better physical fitness of men than women aged over 60.
3. Physically active people achieved better time than physically inactive people by more than 2.5 seconds . Increased physical activity affected the reduction of test time. This shows that physical activity significantly improves physical fitness. Age had no significant effect on the times achieved.
4. Three people involved in the research scored the test time between 14 and 20 seconds. This range of time suggests an increased likelihood of the falling of the respondents. These people in particular should conform to the recommendations of exercises for older people suggested in this work.
5. Two people residing in the nursing home achieved the test time of more than 20 seconds. These people apply little or minimal physical activity and suffer from cardiovascular diseases. These people should immediately apply recommendations of exercises for older people to improve

physical fitness body efficiency in order to reduce the risk of suffering from other diseases, improve the quality of life and avoid the possibility of falls.

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